

Multiple Zeta Values and Bell Polynomials

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ABSTRACT:

In this short paper, we establish that certain multiple zeta values satisfy a recurrence relation and can be written in terms of Bell polynomials.

Keywords: Riemann zeta function, Bell polynomials, Recurrence Relation, Multiple zeta values.

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INTRODUCTION

Here we consider the multiple zeta values:

$$\zeta(a, a, \dots, a) := \zeta(\{a\}^n), \quad \zeta(\{a\}^0) = 1; \quad (1)$$

In [1] it was obtained the relation:

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(\{a\}^5) = & \frac{1}{5} \zeta(5a) - \frac{1}{12} \zeta^3(a) \zeta(2a) + \frac{1}{6} \zeta^2(a) \zeta(3a) - \frac{1}{6} \zeta(3a) \zeta(2a) - \frac{1}{4} \zeta(a) \zeta(4a) + \\ & + \frac{1}{8} \zeta^2(2a) \zeta(a) + \frac{1}{120} \zeta^5(a), \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

which can be written in terms of complete Bell polynomials [2, 3]:

$$\zeta(\{a\}^5) = \frac{1}{5!} B_5(0! \zeta(a), -1! \zeta(2a), 2! \zeta(3a), -3! \zeta(4a), 4! \zeta(5a)), \quad (3)$$

and in Sec. 2 we exhibit the corresponding expression for $\zeta(\{a\}^n)$.

MULTIPLE ZETA VALUES IN TERMS OF COMPLETE BELL POLYNOMIALS

The result (3) suggests the formula:

$$\zeta(\{a\}^n) = \frac{1}{n!} B_n(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n), \quad x_j = (-1)^{j-1} (j-1)! \zeta(ja), \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, n, \quad (4)$$

in fact, (4) was deduced in [4-6], and it means the existence of the following recurrence relation [7]:

$$n \zeta(\{a\}^n) = \sum_{j=1}^n (-1)^{j-1} \zeta(ja) \zeta(\{a\}^{n-j}), \quad n \geq 1. \quad (5)$$

From (4) is immediate the result of Rao-Subbarao [8]:

$$\zeta(\{a\}^3) = \frac{1}{5} \zeta^3(a) - \frac{1}{2} \zeta(a) \zeta(2a) + \frac{1}{3} \zeta(3a), \quad (6)$$

and (5) allows obtain the Hoffman-Zagier formula [9]:

$$\zeta(\{2\}^n) = \frac{\pi^{2n}}{(2n+1)!}. \quad (7)$$

It is possible to show the following determinantal expressions:

$$\zeta(\{a\}^2) = \frac{1}{2!} \begin{vmatrix} \zeta(a) & 1 \\ \zeta(2a) & \zeta(a) \end{vmatrix}, \quad \zeta(\{a\}^3) = \frac{1}{3!} \begin{vmatrix} \zeta(a) & 2 & 0 \\ \zeta(2a) & \zeta(a) & 1 \\ \zeta(3a) & \zeta(2a) & \zeta(a) \end{vmatrix}, \quad (8)$$

$$\zeta(\{a\}^4) = \frac{1}{4!} \begin{vmatrix} \zeta(a) & 3 & 0 & 0 \\ \zeta(2a) & \zeta(a) & 2 & 0 \\ \zeta(3a) & \zeta(2a) & \zeta(a) & 1 \\ \zeta(4a) & \zeta(3a) & \zeta(2a) & \zeta(a) \end{vmatrix}, \quad \text{etc.}$$

hence in the general case:

$$\zeta(\{a\}^n) = \frac{1}{n!} \begin{vmatrix} \zeta(a) & n-1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ \zeta(2a) & \zeta(a) & n-2 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \zeta((n-1)a) & \zeta((n-2)a) & \vdots & \dots & 1 \\ \zeta(na) & \zeta((n-1)a) & \dots & \dots & \zeta(a) \end{vmatrix}. \quad (9)$$

Finally, the inversion of (4) is given by:

$$\zeta(na) = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{k=1}^n (-1)^{n-k} (k-1)! B_{n,k}(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_{n-k+1}), \quad y_j = j! \zeta(\{a\}^j), \quad (10)$$

in terms of partial Bell polynomials [10, 11].

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